

The Contestation of Power Between Newsrooms and Media Owners in Television Stations in Indonesia

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Abstract

This article describes the contest for power and influence that goes on behind the scenes of Indonesian television broadcasting stations. There is a dynamic relationship between agent and structure – journalists and media owners – in news broadcasting in Indonesian television stations. The newsroom was previously idealised as an independent, neutral space free from intervention, but its independence has been eroded by political contestations involving media owners. Politics relies greatly on the dissemination of information to rally support from constituents. Television is currently the most powerful medium for that purpose. This research is a qualitative study that obtained data from two of Indonesia's largest television stations, Metro TV and TV One. Data collection involved literature review, observation, and in-depth interviews. The obtained data was analysed in three steps: (1) data processing, (2) data reduction, and (3) data display to allow for conclusion drawing. The results of this research show that media owners have significant influence over the content of news broadcasts. This is largely due to a lack of strict government legislation guaranteeing newsroom independence from capital influences that exist in the television industry. Indonesian culture also plays a role in how powerful the regulations that protect the interests and policies of capitalists are.

Keywords: television; broadcasting; newsroom; media owners

Introduction

The development of the media in the context of the dissemination of information in the Reformation Era has led to the proliferation of media stations in various regions of Indonesia. The demands of the 1998 Reformation Movement made freedom of speech the basic right of the whole community. The presence of new media stations was a source of momentum behind the dissemination of information. Unexpectedly, the media has become more associated with breakthroughs in information technology. Media convergence has become a

common term. Information is not spread through mainstream media alone, but also via new chains of communication that link all media affiliates. Control of this information network is the end goal of "world domination".

Television as a visual and auditory medium act as the eyes and ears of the modern information community and has three primary roles: it serves as a medium for information, education, and entertainment. The openness of the media sector to investments, guaranteed by law, has led to its massive development in Indonesia. Broadcasting Law Number 32 of 2002 opened the doors to government interference in response to the rapid growth of the powers of the broadcast media. Control of information was an important foundation of several new regulations.

The development of politics was also affected by these changes in the mechanisms of Indonesian democracy, with potentially significant impact on the ebb and flow of information. The mechanisms of politics naturally place great emphasis on image branding and optics. Such conditions inherently create demand for the involvement of media institutions, as information distributors, in politics. The demand for media as an important tool for branding and optics has led to favouritism in its use for such purposes.

So intense is the democratic process in this country. Due to the demand for branding, there is an ever-increasing focus on television as a popular medium for enhancing an individual's image and branding. At every political level in this country, including elections at the district/city level, provincial elections, legislative elections, and presidential elections, television plays a dominant role in the dissemination of information and how the information is served. Without hesitation, many television stations, such as Metro TV ("Knowledge to Elevate") and TVOne ("Election TV"), have made a brand for themselves as serving purely political content.

According to Graeme Turner (1991:128-129), television programming at its core accommodates social practices that constantly represent social reality. A number of television programmes are capable of producing social reality and involve dynamic and complex interactions and negotiations between a number of parties. Without exception, television programming packaged within the context of political image branding has become the target of complex and dynamic interactions and negotiations.

These interactions and negotiations involve three stages: pre-broadcast, broadcast, and post-broadcast stages. The pre-broadcast stage, for example, involves an in-house or out-house production team. In each stage of production, there are several parties with their own personal interests, such as the editor-in-chief, producers, executive producers, assistant executive producers, coverage coordinator, documentation team, editors, visual and quality control team, editor secretary, news team, and even news sources and informants.

Research Method

This study used the qualitative research methodology, which puts more emphasis on processes rather than outcomes and tend to involve the relationship of trust between the researcher and the informant. The subjects of this research are news journalists working for television stations in Indonesia, specifically those involved directly in the production process of news coverage on television.

The informants were media workers and owners of television stations. The informants include news producers, legal officers, heads of news agencies, broadcasting regulation makers, and broadcast monitoring teams.

This research was conducted at two national television stations, TVOne and MetroTV. Data was collected through observation, in-depth interviews, and documentation study. Data analysis was done in three stages: data processing, data reduction, and data display with interpretation. A conclusion was drawn from the results of the data analysis.

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